

BURST Horizon Europe project

BREAKING LIMITS USING RECORD ENABLING SILICON TECHNOLOGY WITH PHOTONIC MANAGEMENT

A 36-month EU-funded project which will explore methods to improve Photovoltaic cells' efficiency and cost thanks to innovative light trapping, passivation and metallization methods.

The BURST project involving 9 partners from 6 countries was officially launched on May 1st, 2024 with a Kick-Off Meeting held on May 29th and 30th in Brussels, Belgium.

About the project

The BURST project supports the efforts of a strategic European IBC (interdigitated back-contact) crystalline silicon (c-Si) technology by improving the power conversion efficiency towards the practical limits. BURST will achieve efficiencies of at least 26% with thin (<80 µm) and 27% with thick c-Si photovoltaic (PV) cells, without relying on critical materials like indium or silver. Leveraging on the expertise of leading IBC experts and pioneering groups in light management, passivation and metallization for Si PV, BURST will develop the next generation of IBC cells with innovative and industrially scalable photonic light management, superior passivation schemes and Ag-free metallization.

Maximizing the absorption of light in ever thinner wafers requires advanced light management. BURST's light trapping based on optimized photonic structures will demonstrate superiority over the state-of-the-art random pyramidal textures by absorbing >99 % of the theoretical limit. BURST will transfer lab-type fabrication processes to cost-effective, high-throughput industrial fabrication methods (TRL5) by using high precision, rapid laser patterning and atmospheric dry etching.

Advanced passivation and passivating contacts are essential to prevent recombination and harvest the extra charge carriers generated from the advanced light management. BURST's IBC cell front side will achieve excellent passivation (enabling >750 mV) and high transparency. Alloying BURST's excellent poly-Si passivating rear contacts with oxygen will mitigate parasitic absorption at the rear side. BURST will apply aluminium and copper as inexpensive and abundant materials with low-cost techniques to ensure a low-resistive contact (<1 mOhm.cm²) to the passivating poly-Si contact of the Ag-free BURST IBC cell.

Finally, the high-efficiency BURST cells will be assembled into mini-modules supplemented by detailed analysis of the costs, environmental impact, supply security and circularity to demonstrate the advantage of BURST technology in relevant environments.

Contact details

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Acronym: BURST

Title: Breaking Limits Using Record Enabling Silicon Technology With Photonic Management

Call Identifier: HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-11 - Advanced concepts for crystalline Silicon technology

GA number: 101146684

Project costs: €3 214 191,50

Duration: 36 months; start 1 May 2024

Beneficiaries

9 beneficiaries

ISFH is a leading research institution dedicated to advancing the field of solar energy. ISFH has consistently been at the forefront of ground-breaking research and technological innovation in photovoltaics, solar thermal technologies, and energy storage. ISFH team is composed of renowned scientists, engineers, and researchers collaborating to develop cutting-edge solutions that drive the widespread adoption of solar energy, contributing to a cleaner and more sustainable future.

TUD is a prestigious technical university in the Netherlands, excels in engineering, science, and technology. With a rich history, TUD's diverse community drives innovation, tackling global challenges. Fostering creativity, entrepreneurship, they equip graduates for positive societal impact. Pioneering research, industry collaboration shape a sustainable, advanced future.

MBE, an institute of the Leibniz Universität Hannover, in Hannover, Germany, advances electronic materials, devices. Fostering collaborations with industry, academia, it drives tech breakthroughs for electronics, IT, communication systems. Emphasizing excellence in research, teaching, knowledge transfer, MBE prepares skilled professionals for the future.

ISC in Konstanz, Germany, pioneers solar tech and solutions. Renowned hub for research and innovation, it tackles global energy challenges. Diverse, skilled team explores photovoltaics, solar thermal, energy storage, pursuing efficiency, cost-effectiveness, sustainability breakthroughs.

NINES PV is an innovative SME in solar cell processing and manufacturing. Committed to sustainability, efficiency, their visionary team develops advanced photovoltaic tech, reducing costs and environmental impact. They patented a unique, low water and CO2 footprint processing technology. This efficient etching method can replace inefficient wet processing, enabling advanced solar cell architectures at low cost and high throughput.

UNINOVA jointly advances knowledge and technologies across disciplines. A vibrant hub for R&D, encouraging collaboration among researchers, professors and students. The Nanophotonics and PV team involved in BURST has gained global recognition, enhancing solar cell efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and flexibility. UNINOVA's expertise and software facilities support modeling design for innovative, optimized devices enhanced with photonics structures.

CEA, is a world-leading institution for solar research, based in France. INES lab drives renewable energy transformation. Experts explore photovoltaics, solar thermal, and new solutions, advancing solar efficiency, storage, and integration through research and industry collaborations.

HOLO/OR pioneers beam shaping, optical design. Focused on innovation, it's a global leader in advanced diffractive optics. Specializing in custom elements, shaping laser beams with precision, efficiency. Harnessing diffractive optics optimizes laser performance, enhances efficiency in diverse applications: material processing, medical devices, 3D printing.

BENKEI is a French consulting company with over 30 years of experience in research and innovation support with expertise in large consortium collaborative projects.